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A STUDY OF PARTS OF SPEECH USED IN ONLINE THAI FOOD RECIPES

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ABSTRACT

This case study aims to study parts of speech used in online Thai food recipes from an online cooking website and to examine which parts of speech are frequently used in an online cooking website. The material in this study was 40 Thai food recipes that are selected and analyzed from one online Thai food recipes website. The instrument was a checklist which determines and categorizes parts of speech as nouns, verbs, adverbs, adjectives, pronouns, conjunctions, prepositions and determiners. The data collections were analyzed with the frequency and percentage. The result of the study shows that nouns are the most common part of speech used in an online recipe writing (59%) while pronouns are the least common part of speech found from the study (0%). In conclusion, the most common part of speech found in recipes writing was the noun, while pronouns are the least common part of speech found from the study. The most important thing, in every sentence uses a noun as a subject, as an object and a modifier.

Keywords:

Thai Food Recipe, English Recipe, Parts of Speech.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, English is an international language and widely used around the world. It has been often referred to as a “Global language” of the current era. English plays an important role in many aspects because it is used as an instrument for communication and information sources to transfer thoughts and cultures of people in different countries. It is the language most often studied as a foreign language in the European Union, followed by French, German, and Spanish. It is also the most studied in China, Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. English is also used in textbooks, magazines newspaper and online information. Learning English language is another method that has to learn through food recipes. If the learners practice to write food recipes, they will know parts of speech such as nouns, verbs, pronouns, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions,

conjunctions and determiners. They can learn to copy the pattern of the sentence to write by themselves. In the present global education, online English websites enable students to assimilate many aspects of the English language, especially everyday English. Learning English through online English websites also assists one to practice English by listening, speaking, reading and writing. In the present global education, online English websites enable students to assimilate many aspects of the English language, especially everyday English. Learning English through online English websites also assists one to practice English by listening, speaking, reading and writing. Belch, G'E & Belch, M.A.(2007), explain that the website is important to organizations and is recognized by all industries including education organization and institutions. The main benefit of English learning websites is that millions of students can be reached. Research has shown that total internet growth in Asia has increased more than 40% from 2000 to 2008 (Internet World States, 2008).

Food is an important and sensitive expression of a national culture. At the present time, food shows an even more important character. In Thailand, food does not establish the culture but it is also a trading item heading for improving the countries' economies by exporting local ingredients and human resources. The Thai government cooperated with private sectors has been attempting to present and promote Thai food into the world market. As a result of the attempt, food recipes, menu, ingredients, it's good to present Thai food to foreigners learn about Thai food. Food has varieties of setting: menus, cookbooks, guidebooks, tourist brochures, journals, including online recipe. In this independent study, foods are studied in parts of speech used in food recipes. The setting is selected for the study of parts of speech in the Thai Kitchen website. Online food recipes website is one of the main media that helps students to understand food, culture and information, because it has various practices, activities and level for the students which they can choose to study, to improve how to use English language. The learner can also study many different kinds of parts of speech, for example nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, conjunctions, prepositions, and determiners. The learners can analyze the functions of parts of speech that are in the recipes. From the reasons mentioned above, the researcher was interested in investigating how the food recipes used parts of speech to make food more interesting and impressive.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to analyze parts of speech used in online Thai food recipes from an online cooking website.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The material of the study was taken from <http://www.thaikitchen.com>. There were 40 Thai recipes to analyze. The study focuses on parts of speech used in the online Thai food recipes. They are nouns, verbs, adverbs, adjectives, pronouns, prepositions, conjunctions and determiners. The selected recipes analyzed in this study consist of several parts. There are some short introduction about background of Thai food, how to eat the food, how to cook the food, location to eat, some parts that inform the readers about number of serving for each menu, and cooking durations. These mentioned parts are not related to the findings; therefore, the researcher did not include it in the analysis process.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The findings in this study will benefit for; the teachers who teach English, who could use it as a new teaching method to improve students' skills, and for Thai students to learn parts of speech through food recipes by reading and following the recipes' instructions and ingredients. The students could learn many vocabulary words through cooking by reading and following the recipe's instruction and they can practice writing skills by creating their own local recipes as well.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

For the last part of literature review, there will be more close features of what other researchers have discovered in terms of English grammar, English grammatical structure, English usage, and typical characteristics of English usage.

Potiantong (2010) mentioned that case study aims to study the genre move structure and lexicon-grammatical features of main dish recipes. 40 recipes are selected and analyzed from one English cookbook. The result of the study shows that; the noun is the mostly part of speech used in recipe writing (44.018%) while the pronoun is the least part of speech found from the study (0.355%). The most common structures of the recipes are: Introduction, Recipe Name, Relate Information, Ingredients Part, Cooking Instruction, Additional guidance, and SideDish Recipe. In conclusion, the recipe writing is unique unlike other type of writing. The style of recipe writing is shaped by the structure that each part separated and can be seen clearly. The imperative sentences are popular used in this kind of writing more than other kind of sentence.

Chausirisuksakul (2000), investigated 3 aspects of English grammatical skill, including noun phrases, verb phrases, and subject-verb agreement. The result of the study showed that the most problematic areas of the subjects' grammatical skill were subject-verb agreement, verb phrases, and noun phrases, respectively. The confidence on answer selection by subjects illustrated that Thai employees did not master a good level of grammatical skills. The findings of this study encouraged the future research and rethinking on grammatical skill and mastery of Thai employees in the business sector and conducted with surveyed data. The researcher can use this result to implement into the present study.

Meksujit (2002) conducted a study on grammatical structures used in the business sections of The Nation and the Bangkok Post. This study analyzes and compares grammatical structures. The result of the study showed that the structure clause(source)+clause(quote) was used most frequently in both newspapers while the structure clause(source)+that+clause(quote) was used the least frequently. Moreover, the sentences structures that have post modification occur most frequently whereas the structures: adverbial conjunction+clause, clause subordinate conjunction was used only 9.78%. Among four sentence types, complex sentences are most frequently used in both newspapers, followed by simple sentences, compound sentences, and compound-complex sentences respectively. The used of restrictive relative clauses occur more frequently than the usage of non-restrictive relative clauses in both The Nation and the Bangkok Post. In both newspapers, the omission of verb to be in the past participle is used most frequently with

77.46% whereas the omission of verb to be in the present participle is used 22.54%. Active voice is more popularly used in both newspapers than passive voice.

Phanphanich (1999) analyzed English usage in political news in English language newspapers. This purposes were studied the general characteristics of the language usage and analyzed pieces of political news in an English newspaper, Bangkok Post. The finding showed that sentence structures used the most was complex sentences and the least was compound-complex sentences. The omission of the verb to be used the most was past participle and adjective was used the least. The active voice sentence is frequently used in political news.

Somsilpa (2002) conducted a case study on typical characteristics of English usage in both domestic job advertisement and foreign job advertisement. This study analyzes English usage in 3 sections: layout and copywriting, choice of words and grammatical structures in sentences. The finding revealed that English usage between domestic job ads and foreign jobs ads imply some typical characteristics. In the layout and copywriting part, it is found that the layouts of foreign jobs ads are more complex and full of paragraphs. In contrast, the domestic ads contain lists. For grammatical structures, sentences in domestic ads are quite simple and easy for readers, while foreign ads are more complex.

Surin (2005) focused on the use of English in cosmetic advertisement headlines and the samples were analyzed in three aspects: the vocabulary use, the grammatical structure and the types of headlines. The result showed that “nouns” were mostly employed in headline writing. Based on all word frequency, the study also indicated that the adjective “new” is the word that is most frequently used. There are five types of grammatical structures used. The two most popular types are “fragment” and “simple sentence” respectively. In respect to the types of headlines, direct benefit headlines are mostly found.

Suvaree (2006) The language of advertising has long been studied in various aspect, but little research has been undertaken on airline advertisements. In this study, some major figures of speech and persuasive techniques of advertising claims found in 50 advertisements from 43 airlines are thoroughly examined. Besides of the genre of airline advertisements, focusing on the move structure is also analyzed. It was found that the most frequently used figure is alliteration, while the least used is simile. The trend of using figures showed that those related to sound repetition and without meaning change were more popular than those related to comparison and substitution, due to the former having less complexity and no need for interpretation. For advertising claims, the “Scientific or Statistical” claim was often most used while the “Water is Wet and So What” Claim was used least. The result suggested that the claims offering some kinds of clear convincing evidence are employed more than those without, as this helps advertisements to be more believable. For the genre analysis of the airline ads, there are only four ads that contain all six moves in a sequenced order, so the move structure can be taught in a flexible way; Calling Attention, Creating Interest with Advantages, and Asking for Order, as they are most frequently found in the top three ranks and considered to be crucial for achieving the persuasive purpose of airline ads.

Wanithanachakorn (2005) focused on three processes, which are discourse structure, cohesion among the main parts and average article length in genre analysis of singers’ biography web

pages: a case study. The lexical is the cohesive tie which is used the most frequent among the main parts, and the mean of total words per a Web Page is 2310 words. From the results, it can be implied that the aim of singers' Biography Web Pages is mainly to promote the latest albums of singers. The form of structure employed the most in Web Pages is time sequence.

Chumchai (2008) The purpose of this study was to analyze how linguistic features works (i.e. lexical expansion, semantic features and language functions) in the Korean movie synopses. Quotes from 30 movie synopses were selected and analyzed based on theories of linguistic features. There were fifteen kinds of linguistic feature such as prefixes, suffixes, compounding, denotation, connotation, morphology and so forth. Linguistically applied for the analysis process coupled with the examination of cultural perspectives. The current study showed that the linguistic features were used in diverse ways in movie synopses. In the current study, 15 expressions of linguistic features were revealed. Three types of linguistic feature were used more frequently than others: lexical expansion, semantic features and language functions. The linguistic features which were used mostly were lexical expansion and the least features used were coinage. It was also found that linguistic features mostly found in *The King and The clown*. On the other hand, of all movie synopses, *Someone Behind You* was found the least linguistic features.

From researching the document and the studies above, the researcher is interested in using online websites to develop the learning English ability of secondary school students in an effective way.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study focused on analyzing parts of speech used in an online Thai food recipe. The data from this study was quantitative and qualitative.

SETTING AND MATERIAL OF THE STUDY

The selected recipes in this study were based on 40 recipes from <http://www.thaikitchen.com>. This website is not seriously calling itself Thai Kitchen if it wasn't committed to making anything but the most authentic Thai food. There's no faking it. It's about providing the best Thai food experience available to anyone, anytime, without compromising quality for convenience. That's why it use only fresh, natural ingredients selected at harvest for their quality and flavor. With Thai Kitchen, we can say goodbye to Thai food delivery and pricey restaurant meals. The selected section for this study was about Thai food recipes. The researcher chose Thai food recipes to study because they are special and interesting local food for foreigners'

The researcher downloaded 40 recipes from 8 categories of the Thai Kitchen.com. There are 5 recipes from each category as follows; 1) Appetizer: Easy Chicken, Beef, or Pork Stay, Chicken Satay, Thai Chicken and Lettuce Wraps, Tangy Thai Chicken Meatballs, Sweet Chili Wings; 2) Chicken Beef and Pork: Green Curry Chicken with Basil, Chicken with Chile & Basil, Chicken and Broccoli in Peanut Sauce, Red Curry Chicken, Green Curry beef; 3) Rice & Noodles: Thai Fried Rice, Traditional Pad Thai Noodles, Easy Chicken Pad Thai, Easy Shrimp Pad Thai, Chicken Fried Rice; 4) Seafood: Red Curry Shrimp and Vegetables, Green Curry Mussels, Shrimp and Roasted Red Chili Paste Stir-Fry, Thai Kitchen Red Curry Shrimp and Vegetables,

Grilled Thai Salmon; 5) Soup: Chicken Soup with Rice Noodles, Coconut Ginger Soup, Coconut Chicken, Sour Prawn Soup, Chicken Rice Noodles Soup; 6) Salad: Cold Thai Broccoli Salad, Red Curry Chicken Salad Lettuce Wraps, Cold Rice Noodle Salad with Spicy Lime Vinaigrette, Shrimp & Papaya Salad, Cold Thai Noodle Salad; 7) Sauce & Dips, Cucumber Relish, Eggplant Dipping Sauce, Peanut Carrot Sauce, Spicy Pork & Tomato Dip, Sticky Rice Sauce; 8) Vegetables: Green Curry with Vegetables, Basic Vegetable Stir-Fry, Eggplant Satay, Thai Sweet & Spicy Broccoli, Stir-Fried Green Curry Vegetables

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The research instrument in this study was a checklist which determines and categories part of speech and data analysis started with categorizing the words into parts of speech (nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, prepositions, pronouns, determiners, and conjunctions) by part of speech info.com program, After collecting all the analyzed data, the researcher counted to see the frequency and computed the percentage by Microsoft Excel, then the conclusion and discussion are made

RESEARCH PROCEDURE

The procedures of data analysis of this study are; step 1: Analyze the recipes by categorizing the words used in recipes writing into group according to the structure of part of speech, which are divided in to eight categories; nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, prepositions, pronouns, determiners and conjunctions, step2: Categorize the analyzed data, step3: Compute the percentage to get the frequencies of each word, step 4: Analyze the data and make the conclusion and discussion. According to the analysis, the following data is the result of the frequency of parts of speech found in the selected recipes.

DATA COLLECTION AND DATA ANALYSIS

Forty Thai recipes were collected from the selected website “Thai Kitchen.com” There are many types of recipes in the website that have been categorized the recipes by type of dish, which are Appetizer, Chicken Beef and Pork, Rice & Noodles, Seafood, Soup, Salad, Sauce & Dips, and Vegetables. This case study will focus on 5 the dishes from eight categories which were mostly found in previous research in order to find part of speech used in each recipe. With the number of words, the recipes selected in this study have word count approximately 5,000 words. According to the information, good recipes should be concise and not too long but easy to understand and follow. Recipes with 300-500 words are a good length, which is randomly calculated from the online recipes. After the collected data had been categorized, the researcher analyzed all the data in percentages to find out the frequency in each category and conclude the result with clear and concise explanation; they were counted to see the frequency and computed the percentage by Microsoft Excel program, then the conclusion and discussion were made.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Thai food recipes use nouns base from in a total of 3,385 words with 59% that is the highest parts of speech found in the recipe writing; for example, bee, pork, Satay, ingredients, ounces,

chicken, beef, sirloin, steak, chops, strips, bamboo, cloves, coconut milk, red curry paste, breasts, premium fish sauce, peanut satay sauce, directions, meat, skewers, zigzag fashion, place, dish, garlic, fish sauce, pour, marinade, skewers, cover, hours, skewer, marinade, broil, minutes, grill, cup, lemongrass, chicken breasts, mix, lemongrass, bowl, plastic bag, glass dish, marinade, coat, refrigerate, hour, flavor, thread, broil, grill, heat, water, nutrition information, serving, fiber, fat, protein, cholesterol, sodium, calories, ginger, ground chicken, turkey, chestnuts, cilantro, onion, bottom, inch, stalk, pepper, salt, butter, lettuce, Thai dipping sauce, sugar, lime juice, tamarind paste, rice vinegar, Serrano chili, rings, cilantro, skillet, heat, fry, pepper, spoon, saucepan, syrup, reserve, tea, mixture, lettuce, leave, guests, tablespoon, vegetable oil, chicken breasts, bell peppers, snow peas, Jasmine Rice, Spicy Thai Chili Sauce, egg, pound, shrimp, oil, skillet, heat, seconds, garlic, minutes, rice, sauce, fish sauce, minutes, rice, mixture, side, skillet, scramble, set, rice mixture, kick, side, serving, etc.

Verbs base from the recipes were 741 words with 13% that is the second rank in parts of speech found in the recipe writing; for example, cut, skewers, baking, curry, refrigerate, remove, discard, remaining, is, browned, threading, prevents, burning, minced, skewers, curry, cut, add, toss, remove, discard, remaining, is cooked, serve, dipping, soak, threading, prevents, burning, minced, chopped, flakes, taste, leaves, seeded, sliced, add, stir, , refrigerate, chilled, stirring, dissolve, bring, remaining, sweetening, serve, allowing, wraps, curry, cooked, pan, needed, toss, prepare, directed, using, divided, clove, cut, sliced, beaten, use, peeled, deveined, browned, is cooked, is heated, push, blend, balance, duplicate, is searching, concentrates, deveined, cubed, beaten, sprouts, wedges, bring are, tamarind, heated, serving, etc.

Adjective used in the recipes were 690 words with 12% that is the third rank parts of speech found in recipe writing; for example, boneless, skinless, thin, garlic, smooth, overnight, grill, least, fresh, blended, large, reseal, able, small, longer, extra, medium-high, least, galangal, Chinese, garlic, green, crushed, red, large, crushed red, cool, such, iced, own, plain, lean, chili, arrange, blended, sesame, Belgian endive, large nonstick, golden brown, same, browned, excess, sour, salty, traditional, worth, fruity-sour, impossible, Asian, Indian, optional, garlic, firm, unsalted, fresh, large, cold, small, large, medium-high, garlic, pink, lime, classic, exotic, thin, boneless, skinless, unsalted, Fresh, green, lime, large, soft, medium, cold, medium-high, green, lime, cut-up, green, unsalted, fresh, lime, medium, stir-fry, cold, large, medium-high, pink, green, lime.

Preposition used were 510 words with 9 % that is the fourth rank parts of speech found in recipe writing; for example, in, on, into, of, until, if, as, per, though, from, among, with, over, moreover, the word “in” is the most prepositions used in recipe writing “on” and “until” respectively. Conjunctions used were of 239 words with 4 % that is the fifth rank parts of speech found in recipe writing; “and” was used 124 times, “or” was used 94 times, and “but” was used 6 times respectively. Adverbs used were 122 words with 2 % that is the sixth rank part of speech found in recipe writing; for example, well, thinly, just lightly, thoroughly, when, slightly, immediately, aside, meanwhile, only, occasionally, aside, coarsely, longer, no longer, almost, when, easily, evenly, frequently, gently, no, then, not, as well, tightly, however, noticeably first evenly, as, as well. Determiners used were 56 words with 1 % that is the seventh rank parts of speech found in recipe writing; “the” was used 26 times, “a” was used 10 times, “all” was used 7 times, “any” was used 4 times, “all and each” was used 3 times, “an” was used 2 times and “that”

was used only 1 time. Pronoun used were 12 words with 0 % that is the last rank parts of speech found; “it” (showed 4 times), “you” and “your” (each word showed 3 times), and “they” and “their” (each word showed 1 time) in the recipe writing. In contrast, Thai food recipes uses pronouns at least, determiners, adverbs, conjunctions, prepositions, adjectives, verbs and nouns respectively.

Base on the result of the study of the Thai food recipes, the researcher found that using nouns in every recipe is the most important thing, because every sentence uses noun as a subject, object and modifier. Regarding the results, many interesting points could be found and will be discussed in this section. According to the sub-categories mentioned nouns would be discussed in detail below; Noun is used to name a person, animal, place, thing, and abstract idea. In this case study, many nouns were found in recipes. There are 4 sub-categories in noun; common noun, gerund noun, compound noun, and unit word. Common noun this kind of nouns has been mostly found because recipe writing usually contains many nouns. If we look closer in detail, it was found that it consisted of many culinary terminologies, which could be summarized as follows:

Most of materials and ingredients found in this study are both countable and uncountable nouns. The uncountable nouns are most frequently found because many ingredients in cooking terminology are presented in uncountable form such as salt, pepper, heat, etc. The majority of noun that found in recipe writing is also cooking related terms such as “Cooking tools and containers”, for example: bowl, pot, skillet etc.

Gerund noun sometimes when ‘action’ is used as a ‘noun’ it must be in a gerund form or V+ing. According to the result, nouns with V+ing form could be found in low percentage For example: preparing with shrimp or tofu, Drizzle with remaining dressing, 1 pound turkey sausage, casings removed. Compound noun many compound nouns were found in the analysis. Compound nouns are used to give more specific information about someone or something. Three types of compound nouns were found in the result below; Noun + Noun: We use noun in front of other noun as a modifier to specify the main noun such as vegetable oil, garlic cloves, lemon juice etc.; Adjective + Noun: Adjectives are used to clarify the main noun such as fresh red chili, sour cream, , fresh cilantro leaves etc.; Verb + Noun: Verbs are also used to modify the noun, the types of compound noun found in this case study are both past participle and gerund form e.g. baking sheet, cutting board, dried tomatoes etc.; Unit words mostly found in the ingredient part. When cooking, it is important to cook with the correct amount of ingredients so that the food would have good taste. According to the result, many uncountable nouns are found; therefore the unit words are used in order to give the quantity of those ingredients. For example: 1 pound (500 g) large shrimp, peeled and deveined, 2 tbsps vegetable oil, 2 stalks lemongrass.

In conclusion, according to the result of the study, the highest part of speech found in recipes was “noun”, the second was “verb”, while pronoun is the least part of speech found from the study. The result seemed to support with Potiantong (2010) who analyzed part of speech used in English cookbook. The result of that study shows that; noun is the mostly part of speech used in recipe writing (44.018%) while pronoun is the least part of speech found from the study (0.355%) and Saesiew (2005) conducted a case study of the genre of motoring news in the Nation and the Bangkok Post. This study aimed to discover the structure and lexico grammatical

features of the motoring news from the Nation and the Bangkok Post newspapers. Forty motoring news are collected from both newspaper (20 news from each of them). The data analysis focused on three aspects; the frequency of the part of speech, the style of the lead, and the move structure of the motoring news story. The text in motoring news are analyzed and categorized into 8 part of speech; Noun, Pronoun, Adjective, Verb, Adverb, Preposition, Conjunction, and Determiner. The result showed that noun is the most frequently part of speech used in motoring news and there are many kind of noun written in both columns of the Nation and Bangkok Post. These three studies had the same result, it could be explained that “noun” and “verb” is the part of speech used that is important and can be found in many type of media. As Howatt and Widdowson (2004) mentioned that to focus on process of learning with the student’s activities is more effective, the new designed teaching strategy of learning through recipe writing could be a good choice in order to develop the students’ proficiency. It is easy from cooking recipe that should be concise and easy to follow the step. Each section of the recipe is written into order for it can be easy to read and follow the instructions.

4. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

This case study was analyzed and describes in eight categories of part of speech used in an online Thai food recipe with the title “Thai Kitchen Website” from eight categories; appetizer, chicken, beef & pork, rice & noodles, seafood, soup, salad, sauce & dip and vegetables. There are 5 food recipes in each category in total 40 selected food recipes from the website. The researcher maintained the use of data analysis by apparently using the frequency and percentage of various types of part of speech used as a tool to use English language teaching most successfully. In the result of the eight categories of parts of speech; nouns, verbs, adjectives, pronouns, prepositions, conjunctions and determiners to show that nouns were most frequently used part of speech used in the online Thai food recipes; verbs, adjectives, prepositions, conjunctions, adverbs, determiners and pronouns respectively.

Comparing the frequencies of using parts of speech used in an online Thai food recipe; words from parts of speech used the most were nouns with 3,385 words with 59%. Second, there were 741 words with 13% from verbs in all recipes in the website. Third, words from parts of speech used were adjectives with 690 words with 12% in the recipes on the website. Fourth, there were 510 words with 9% from prepositions in the recipes on the website. Fifth, there were 239 words with 4% used of conjunctions in the recipe. Sixth, there were 122 words with 2% used of adverbs in the recipes on the website. Seventh, there were 56 words with 1% used of determiners in the recipes on the website. Finally there were 12 words with 0% used of pronouns in the recipes on the website. Based on all words frequencies, the study showed that pronouns were the least frequently used 0%. The second was determiners used 1%, followed by “adverbs” used at 2%, conjunctions at 4%, prepositions at 9%, adjectives at 12%, adverbs at 13% and the final rank was “nouns” used at 58%. In conclusion, the results of the study, the highest part of speech found in recipes were nouns, while pronouns are the least parts of speech found from the study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings in this study benefit both research readers and other researchers and learners who interest in English language because clearly of part of speech for using and understanding,

saving of time for planning and saving money for learning English language through Thai food recipes in Thai Kitchen Website.

FOR THE RESEARCH READERS

For the teachers who teach ESL courses, this study could help them to develop the course design about part of speech and procedural writing in order to improve the skill of the learners. For ESL students, this study can be a good example to learn English writing through recipe writing. For the recipe writers who work in cooking's recipe related fields, this study could help them to write a good recipe. Other materials such as movies, songs, tales, newspapers, advertisements, etc. should be considered to study as well. The scope of study could be broadened to include a larger material of online recipes to get more details.

FOR OTHER RESEARCHERS

There are other fields of interests in genre analysis in recipe writing such as genre analysis in bakery recipes, desert recipes, etc. This case study was conducted on English recipes. They would be interesting if the study conducted in other languages to see the differences. This case study conducted based on an online recipe, it would be interesting if the study conducted in other website from different authors to see the difference of language use or move structure.

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